

ROLE OF INDIVIDUAL IN CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCE

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ROLE OF AN INDIVIDUAL IN GENERATION RESOURCE DEMAND

At the back of demand for each and every commodity there are isolated choices made by "consumers". Each individual as a consumer has every right to choose what she/he prefers within the income level. Although consumer as an entity is free to choose whatever he/she prefers but careless choice for resource use can lead to a situation where we eventually use up all over resources such as water, mineral, land etc at a rate which is not sustainable. So, a rational consumer has the responsibility to make his/her choice prudent and far-sighted. This also includes being careful about the wastage and creating demand for newer forms of goods and services that ensure a sustainable life style for higher number of people on earth. At each stage of daily life the consumer gets chance to choose between different forms of appliance having different implications for conservation.

CONSERVATION AT HOME

Starting with the home, the potential of conservation is there at every stage of day to day life one of the most important resources that could be discussed first is the water resource simply being careful about water not flowing out of the tap unnecessarily can save the scarce resource being washed in gallon. Besides, flowing as consumer one should be very careful about what type of water he/she choose for what purpose. For example using up drinking water for any little washing purpose is to wastage one good measure for conservation of water is rain water harvesting.

Not only that a careful consumer who prefers apple coming from Kashmir rather than Australia is actually saving thousands of kilometers of good miles, that distance any food travels to cater the demand of consumer. It not only thus generates a demand for domestic product but eventually reduces fuel needed for food-transportation. Similarly, demand for fresh vegetables instead of refrigerated one reduces the electricity requirement for refrigeration at a large scale.

An alternative choice of appliances used at home has huge. Energy and resource saving potential a 24 watt tube light generates no less lumen than a 100 watt bulb. Energy saving is even higher in case of CFL bulbs. Given the life time's energy saving potential and amenity generated the consumer finally could incur a system of lower cost by purchasing efficient lighting system even the initial purchase price is higher. Same thing could be said for the CFC free refrigerators which emits no CFC one of the most powerful greenhouse gases. Note energy efficiency Bureau in India has implemented five star system where higher number of stars for any appliance would imply higher level of energy efficiency.

Finally, demand for waste disposal system not only helps to sustain a cleaner environment but also generates the scope of waste treatment in many cases.

CONSERVATION IN TRANSPORT

Transport sector has huge resource saving potential use of public transport is a good way of conserve huge amount of resource per head. Consumer can basically play a very important role in the sense, if they generate large demand for comfortable public transport, then investors (both public and private) will be invested in investing in the same sector. It not only reduces per capita energy use, but also has huge potential in lowering emission. Also more use of pollution free vehicles such as bicycle, trams which eventually has not very now energy requirement could play an important role in energy conservation. Similarly fes pedserian demand could not only result in clean pavements, the beautification can be done by tree plantation plying crucial role in pollution absorption.

CONSERVATION AT WORK PLACE

At work place also very simple things such as putting the right off when not needed, use if individual air conditioning machine instead of Central cooling system can result in lot of energy conservation because, in all the rooms in an office, the need of cooling is not likely to be same.

EQUITABLE USE OF RESOURCES FOR SUSTAINABLE LIFE STYLE

Resource Conservation has an important implication for increase in equity in resource use. This equity had never been at place. It has been generated location of resource itself is random. For example 56% of world oil reserve is situated in the Middle East countries. Besides, it is aggravated by the inequitable population growth and resulting varying population density across nations and inequitable distribution of income. It resulted in unequal resource use. For example per capita energy use in India is 23 times lower than that of USA (531 KG OE in India and 7,290 KG OE in USA). It resulted in inequality in emission. Although per capita emission countries like India and China are growing faster, still they are for behind other developed nation. Per capita CO2 emission in USA is 19.9 metric ton as compared to 1.2 metric ton in India.

SUSTAINABLE LIFE STYLE

Sustainable life style requires some basic consciousness regarding the use of energy. They are as follows:-

- (1) Instead of converting forest land to agricultural land, make the use of existing land for multiple cropping.
- (2) Increase in irrigation.
- (3) Not burning crop residues that emit CO2
- (4) Use of paper and jute bags instead of non-recyclable bags.
- (5) Use of energy efficient appliances like CFL bulbs, keep bulbs and tubes cleans dust decrease efficiency by 20% to 30%.
- (6) Pressure cooker can save up to 75% energy in cooking.
- (7) Use of public transport system.

These demands could be generated from the part of consumer and awareness from this part this can lead to energy saving and conservation which could be utilized in reduction in this inequality.

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